

APPENDIX A

Specification matrix of the assessment

Table A.1

Specification Matrix of the CPS Assessment

Stage	Item	CPS Skill	Description
0	1	A2 Discovering the type of collaborative interaction to solve the problem, along with goals	TT must identify that talking through the chat they can make agreements to solve the problem.
	2	A1 Discovering perspectives and abilities of team members	TT must discover what his/her teammates see on their tablets and conclude that they all see the same thing.
	3	A3 Understanding roles to solve problem	TT must identify that each one was assigned a color and that corresponds to the star color they should look for.
1	4	B1 Building a shared representation and negotiating the meaning of the problem (common ground)	TT must conclude with his/her teammates that there are several solutions and that they must agree.
	5	B3 Describe roles and team organisation (communication protocol/rules of engagement)	TT must understand what roles / colors his teammates have and communicate his / her own, in order to organize and compromise the rules of the game.
	6	C1 Communicating with team members about the actions to be/ being performed	TT and his/her teammates must devise a plan and communicate to execute it and achieve the task.
	7	C2 Enacting plans	TT and his teammates execute the plan, each one has a responsibility regarding the plan they discussed.
	8	D1 Monitoring and repairing the shared understanding	TT monitors or reinforces what they understand about the problem and reiterates the importance of following the plan.
2	9	D2 Monitoring results of actions and evaluating success in solving the problem	TT asks or communicates their doubts about what they should do, evaluates the achievement of the task and reinforces the idea of communicating to achieve the solution.
	10	B2 Identifying and describing tasks to be completed	TT asks or communicates changes in the objectives of the problems, particularly when it moves to a next stage.
	12	C1 Communicating with team members about the actions to be/ being performed	TT and his/her teammates must devise a plan and communicate to execute it and achieve the task.
	13	C2 Enacting plans	TT and his/her teammates execute the plan, each one has a responsibility regarding the plan they discussed.
	14	D1 Monitoring and repairing the shared understanding	TT monitors or reinforces what they understand about the problem and reiterates the importance of following the plan.
	15	D2 Monitoring results of actions and evaluating success in solving the problem	TT asks or communicates their doubts about what they should do, evaluates the achievement of the task and reinforces the idea of communicating to achieve the solution.
	3	16	B2 Identifying and describing tasks to be completed

	17	C3 Following rules of engagement, (e.g., prompting other team members to perform their tasks.)	Given that at this stage they are not explicitly assigned a color, TT must be organized with their peers to define their roles.
	18	C1 Communicating with team members about the actions to be/ being performed	TT and his/her teammates must devise a plan and communicate to execute it and achieve the task.
	19	C2 Enacting plans	TT and his/her teammates execute the plan, each one has a responsibility regarding the plan they discussed.
	20	D3 Monitoring, providing feedback and adapting the team organisation and roles	TT evaluates whether his/her teammates followed the rules of engagement, on what color to choose or communicates their doubts.
4	21	B2 Identifying and describing tasks to be completed	TT asks or communicates changes in the objectives of the problems, particularly when it moves to a next stage.
	22	C3 Following rules of engagement, (e.g., prompting other team members to perform their tasks.)	Given that at this stage they are not explicitly assigned a color, TT must be organized with their peers to define their roles.
	23	C1 Communicating with team members about the actions to be/ being performed	TT and his/her teammates colleagues must devise a plan and communicate to execute it and achieve the task.
	24	C2 Enacting plans	TT and his/her teammates execute the plan, each one has a responsibility regarding the plan they discussed.

Note: The first column corresponds to the stage or level of the activity; The second column is the item; The third column indicates the skill CPS defined by the OECD (OECD, 2017); And finally, the fourth column is a brief item description, where TT corresponds to the student evaluated (Test Taker).